

A Different Approach to What the Pandemic Has Taught on Education

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Abstract

A report on the improvement in distance education due to the pandemic has been prepared jointly by UNESCO, UNICEF and the World Bank. The next generation of students risk losing \$17 trillion in present value, or about 14 percent of today's global GDP. It has created school closures and economic shocks related to COVID-19. This new projection far exceeds the \$10 trillion estimate published in 2020 and reveals that the impact of the pandemic is more severe than previously thought. The pandemic and school closures have not only endangered children's health and safety, with the rise of domestic violence and child labor , but also significantly impacted student learning. The report shows that in low- and middle-income countries, the share of children living in Learning Poverty, which was already over 50 percent before the Pandemic, could reach 70 percent, largely due to prolonged school closures and the relative ineffectiveness of distance education . If action is not taken, learning losses can continue to accumulate after children return to school and will be in a position to jeopardize their future learning. Results from global simulations of severe learning losses and worsening inequalities in education, the impact of school

closures on learning, are now supported by country estimates of actual learning losses. Evidence from Brazil, rural Pakistan, rural India, South Africa and Mexico, among others, indicates significant losses in mathematics and reading. In some low- and middle-income countries, on average, learning losses are roughly proportional to the duration of the closures – that is, each month that schools are closed will result in a full month of learning losses.

Keywords: *Pandemic and Education Process, Distance Education in Pandemic, Effects of Pandemic on Education, Education Alternatives in Pandemic*

1. Introduction

The extent of learning loss varies considerably between and within countries by subject, socioeconomic status, gender and age of students, or grade level. For example, results from some countries show significant learning losses in reading and mathematics for 10–15-year-old students.

The estimated learning losses were greater in math than in reading and disproportionately affected younger students, low-income students and girls. The expected share of learning in a school year standardized by the length of closures shows different results in different countries. Children, children and girls from low-income households were less likely to access distance learning due to limited electricity, connectivity, devices, accessible technologies, as well as discrimination and social and gender norms. Younger students had less access to age-appropriate distance learning and were more affected by learning loss than older students. Preschoolers, who are at a crucial stage for learning and development, faced a double disadvantage as they were often excluded from distance learning and school reopening plans.

As a result, these children are at risk of missing out on much of the support that schools and learning can provide for their well-being and life chances.

2. Learning Recovery Response

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The learning recovery response should target support to those most in need to prevent growing inequalities in education. Beyond learning, growing evidence demonstrates the negative impact of school closures on students' mental health and well-being, health and nutrition, and protection, reinforcing the vital role schools play in providing comprehensive support and service to students. How should decision makers and the international community respond to the growing global education crisis? Reopening and keeping schools open have been a top priority globally. While nearly every country in the world offered distance learning opportunities to students, such initiatives differed in quality and reach, and in many cases offered an inadequate alternative to face-to-face education. Stopping and reversing learning losses, especially for the most vulnerable students, requires face-to-face education. Decision makers need to reassure parents and caregivers of the global evidence that with adequate safety measures such as social distancing, masking and improved ventilation, children can safely continue in face-to-face education.

Here are four ways universities can prepare education for the future impact of COVID-19 on work and education:

3. Learning Recovery Programs

Countries need to establish Learning Recovery Programs. Three lines of action will be crucial:

1. Unifying the curriculum – helping teachers to prioritize key material that students miss while out of school, even if the content is often covered in earlier grades, to ensure that the curriculum is aligned with students' learning levels. Increasing the time to achieve basic math and literacy attainment, for example by reducing the number of lessons taught by reinforcing the 1st and 2nd grade curriculum.
2. Extending the study period – extending the school day, changing the academic calendar to extend the school year, or offering summer school to all students or those in need.
3. To increase the efficiency of learning by supporting teachers in structured pedagogy and targeted teaching practices. Much more funding will be needed for the immediate recovery

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of learning if countries are to prevent the long-term damage they are currently facing in productivity and inclusion.

4. Improving Learning

Accelerating improvement in learning has benefits that go far beyond short-term gains:

It can give children the foundations for lifelong learning and help countries increase efficiency, equity and resilience. This can be achieved if countries build on investments made and lessons learned during the crisis, with a particular focus on six areas:

1. *Assessing student learning so that instruction can be targeted to students' learning levels and specific needs.*
2. *Investing in digital learning opportunities for all students, ensuring technology is fit for purpose, and focusing on improving human interactions.*
3. *Strengthening support that strengthens the role of parents, families and communities in children's learning.*
4. *Ensuring teachers are supported and have access to practical, high-quality professional development opportunities, teaching guides and learning materials.*
5. *Increasing the share of education in the national budget allocation and linking stimulus packages to the above-mentioned investments that can accelerate learning.*
6. *Investing in evidence-building – specifically, application research to understand what works and how to scale what works at the system level.*

It is time to move from crisis intervention to learning recovery. We must ensure that investments and actions to improve learning lay the foundation for more efficient, equitable and resilient education systems—systems that truly deliver learning and well-being for all children and young people. Only then can we ensure the continuity of learning in the face of future disruptions. The coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic has caused an unprecedented crisis in all areas. This emergency in the field of education has led to the massive closure of face-to-face activities of

educational institutions in more than 190 countries in order to prevent the spread of the virus and reduce its impact. According to data from the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), by mid-May 2020, more than 1.2 billion students of all education levels worldwide had stopped attending face-to-face education.

including 22 countries that offer both methods (offline and online) , 4 with online-only modalities and 2 with offline-only modalities.

To make adjustments, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of the national or sub-national curriculum, the resources and capacities of the country to develop distance education processes, the levels of discrimination and educational inequality in the country, and how much of the school year is.

However, several countries in the region have national digital education strategies with a model leveraging ICTs (Alvarez Marinelli et al., 2020). This is further complicated by unequal access to an Internet connection, resulting in an unequal distribution of resources and strategies⁴ that mainly affects low-income or more vulnerable groups (Rieble-Aubourg and Viteri , 2020). The ¹pandemic has transformed the contexts in which the curriculum is implemented, not only because of the use of platforms and the need to take into account conditions other than those for which the curriculum was originally designed, but also because certain knowledge and competences are more relevant in the current situation.

5. School Systems

A number of decisions need to be made and resources made available, which poses a challenge for school systems, educational institutions and teachers. This applies to the curricular adjustments and prioritization and contextualization needed to ensure content is relevant to the current

¹ To address this situation, authorities should prioritize efforts aimed at maintaining contact and continuity of education with populations living in the least favorable social and economic conditions and more difficult to connect, on the one hand, to support homeschooling processes, and, on the other hand, address the differences that will deepen during this crisis. and inequalities, protocols should be designed to continue and maintain education when schools eventually reopen.

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emergency, based on consensus among all relevant stakeholders . Equally important, these adjustments should prioritize currently outstanding competencies and values such as solidarity, self-learning, care for oneself and others, social-emotional skills, health and resilience, among others. A controversial and complex issue is decision-making criteria and approaches regarding learning priorities and how to make adjustments. An alternative is to choose curriculum content that is more relevant and takes precedence over others. Another possibility is to integrate content and learning objectives into interdisciplinary thematic clusters, using project or research methodologies that allow for a unified interaction, allowing simultaneous consideration of various topics through topics relevant and relevant to students, especially in the current context (*approach to learning*). Under this approach, teachers' independence and developing complex competencies among teachers should be valued.

Some countries have prepared curriculum prioritization recommendations that include a reduced set of core learning objectives across different disciplines, moving from curriculum prioritization to existing curriculum, adopting a modular approach to content by level, moving from basic education to new learning associated with integrated or meaningful learning.

Curriculum adaptation should address aspects such as flexibility and contextualization , prioritization of learning objectives and content that enable better understanding and response to crisis, inclusion of care and health - related aspects , critical and reflective thinking and understanding of information and news.²

Meanwhile, a middle ground must be found between identifying the core skills that will be essential for the continuation of education and deepening the all-encompassing and humanistic character of education. This should be done without the pressure of emphasizing only instrumental learning. Similarly, the demands of groups with specific needs should be taken into account when changing the curriculum and creating pedagogical tools. For students with disabilities or living in a variety of conditions and environments that make it difficult for them to continue their education,

² social and economic trends, and encouraging behavior that is empathetic, tolerant and non-discriminatory, among other things.

for example, changes must be made and necessary assistance provided so that they can continue. It is also necessary to take into account the linguistic and cultural differences that exist between indigenous groups and immigrant populations. Similarly, a sexist perspective must be brought to light and halt cases of gender-based violence or inequality that may worsen while the facility is under quarantine.

6. Countries' Readiness for Online Continuing Education

At present it is not possible to say with certainty what impact the crisis will have on the implementation of the curriculum at various levels of primary and secondary education; however, existing differences in learning achievement are predicted to worsen due to unequal access to curriculum coverage and existing educational disparities. The Internet provides one-on-one, as most countries choose to maintain the continuity of education through the use of online resources. The abundance of pedagogical resources and information, and the variety of communication tools available, provide ideal platforms to bring schools and the learning process closer to home and students in isolation. Although significant progress has been made in reducing gaps in access to the digital world, especially supported by the widespread availability of mobile connectivity, significant gaps still remain in material access to the digital world (ECLAC, 2019; Trucco and Palma , 2020). When we compare those living in urban areas with those living in rural areas, it is stated that approximately 42 percent of those living in urban areas have internet access at home, while only 14 percent of those living in rural areas have access to the internet (ECLAC, 2019).

These numbers skyrocket when mobile Internet connectivity is included ; however, statistics on this subject are only available to a small number of countries. About 80 percent of 15-year-old students in the region who took the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) exam in 2018 had internet access at home, while only 61 percent had access to a computer. By comparison, more than half of students in OECD countries had homeschool software, while only a third of students in the United States had access to such software. Although the majority of students in the

region have an internet connection, the majority of students are still completely closed, especially in countries where resources are scarce.

7. Use of the Internet for Socializing and Entertainment-Related Activities

the use of the Internet for activities related to socialization and entertainment does not begin until adolescence, primary school students are likely to be at a disadvantage in continuing education online (Trucco and Palma , 2020). In the medium and long term, preparing to bridge this wider digital divide fosters virtuous synergies of social and cultural inclusion for children and adolescents . These synergies offer opportunities for a child's entire life and the skills necessary to deal with future crises. Alongside the competencies and training activities that are part of cognitive learning, it is essential to develop self-care and effective risk management strategies and to teach students how to protect themselves as internet users. This is especially important in light of current conditions, where children and adolescents are spending more time online than ever before. Not all start with the same level of knowledge, attitude, and learning necessary to develop and adopt coping strategies that will enable them to make the most of the opportunities the Internet has to offer, while minimizing or dealing with risks. use (Trucco and Palma , 2020).

Similarly, not all educators are equipped to provide and promote online education continuity, as will be shown in the following discussion:

- *Obtain content from the school website by downloading, installing or viewing*
- *Keep in touch with instructors using social networking sites*
- *Using social networking sites as a means of communicating with other students on academic matters*
- *Internet Using educational applications or websites on a personal computer to search for relevant content on the Internet, e.g. to find explanations, to follow lectures*

Agenda for Sustainable Development , which includes the values of justice and inclusion , the standards were revised in 2011 and 2018 . These revisions were made in 2018. The UNESCO ICT

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Competence Framework is a document that defines 18 competencies for teachers. These competences are organized around six aspects of teaching practice (understanding ICT in education policy ; curriculum and assessment; pedagogy; application of digital skills; organization and management; and teacher professional learning) and at three levels of pedagogical use of ICT by teachers:

- *information ,*
- *knowledge deepening and*
- *knowledge creation (UNESCO, 2018a).*

integrate information and communication technology (ICT) knowledge into their daily work are in a better position to provide high-quality education to their students and effectively foster the growth of their students' ICT. Although these standards have been in place for some time, few institutions have implemented them to replace initial teacher training programs. This is done so that the next generation of educators can develop the skills necessary for education in the twenty-first century.

8. Adapting Evaluation Procedures to Individual Needs

Adopting appropriate pedagogical activities to understand and improve schoolchildren's learning progress requires evaluating and monitoring their educational experience, as well as providing feedback on these educational experiences. Through distance education activities, the formative importance of evaluations was emphasized. By learning about specific learnings from each student's diagnosis and follow-up tasks, teachers can offer feedback and modify teaching tactics to make them more successful. This knowledge can be obtained through exercises. In addition, the development of formative assessment and self-assessment tools facilitates the involvement of teachers and students in the process of working together to assess students' and teachers' own progress towards intended learning outcomes . Similarly, revisions to guidelines or policies are necessary to address concerns about class promotion and the implementation of standardized or large-scale exams . Some countries have decided to avoid retraining in favor of continuity and

improvement in education over the next few years. Other countries have chosen to either cancel or delay assessments or to implement alternative strategies and methodologies for testing and validating student learning.

It is also important to monitor students' learning and the effects of strategies implemented in the current context, in preparation for the reopening of schools. Second, more work is needed to identify mechanisms that ensure equity in evaluation processes. This is especially important in light of the fact that the current crisis continues to have an impact on various aspects of exam preparation, such as the progress of learning, the availability of infrastructure, and even the state and development of the social-emotional situation.

Finally, there is no universal solution that can be applied to all nations. The pandemic has varying impacts and degrees of severity in every nation, and the ongoing nature of the crisis requires rapid and creative responses tailored to the needs of individual communities. To this end, it is necessary to work with teachers and experts from academia and other sectors to draw on the experience of other nations and expand the potential to create curricula and assessment systems.

9. Importance of providing assistance to teaching staff and school administration

Teachers and education staff as a whole have played a crucial role in the response to the COVID-19 pandemic and have had to address a variety of different evolving demands across the school. Many teachers have had to not only re-plan and adapt their educational processes, including adjusting methods and curricula, designing materials, and diversifying the media, formats and platforms used, but also to take part in activities to protect students' material safety.

It has become increasingly important for teachers and other education personnel to meet the challenges of providing socio-emotional and mental health support to students and their families. Due to the pandemic, this aspect of their business has become more and more demanding. In conducting their teaching activities and meeting these new demands, teachers often discover that they lack the training and resources necessary to address the challenges of adapting teaching

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content and formats to the needs of students living in disadvantaged conditions. Even before the pandemic, there were limited opportunities for teachers in the region to receive inclusive education (UNESCO, 2018b) or interact with students in less desirable and more diverse settings (UNESCO, 2013).

Additionally, as a result of recent changes in the situation, educators are now required to use virtual platforms and methods that they may or may not be familiar with. The situation is similar around the world, although the majority of Latin American countries participating in the latest International Teaching and Learning Survey (TALIS) conducted by the OECD (2019) reported that they received training in the use of information and communication technology (ICT) for teaching as part of teachers.

Similarly, the use of new technologies in educational environments where it is applicable necessitates providing support and training to educators. These new formats require teachers to be trained and empowered to make decisions in the classroom. These decisions should take into account the curricular guidelines of each country and the circumstances and conditions of its students. While professionals from various fields have to make materials and resources available on various platforms throughout the pandemic, faculty in particular need time and direction to have the appropriate knowledge to study, understand and make judgments about their use. The use of virtual systems in the classroom carries with it the risk of classroom dispersion, due to the potential for overexposure of both teachers and students, as well as the difficulties in maintaining healthy teacher-student relationships and the mediation of conflicts that may arise from COVID-19.

This creates emotional fatigue, feelings of frustration and tension among teaching staff . To create and execute educational solutions to social and health crises, there must be active participation of all parties involved in education, both during quarantine times and in the process.

Improvements must be made in the ability of management teams to find creative, contextual responses to organizational, teaching, and support issues for teachers so that they can address educational continuity, socio -emotional support, and strengthening the social role of schools. These improvements should be made possible through improved management teams' ability to

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find these answers. It is also extremely important to empower teachers and other members of education staff to make contextual and adaptive pedagogical decisions, while striking a healthy balance between independence and providing assistance. In addition, the responsibilities of education workers regarding the upbringing, care and livelihood of their children should also be taken into account. Significant numbers of educators, including teachers and other education workers, do not have employment contracts where they are permanent, work for many employers, or are paid hourly or by subject basis.

equipment was delivered directly to trainers in some countries, emphasis was placed on the supply of 2,500 laptops with internet connectivity to 504 educational institutions in indigenous villages. This decision was made because the coronavirus is not circulating in these communities, as well as the way family and community coexistence means that "the school is in the community" and ties with teachers are severed as a result. In addition, this decision was made because the way they lived together as a family and in the community meant that "the school is in the community" (Office of the President of the Republic of Paraguay, 2020).

Maintaining employment, salary and benefits for teachers, as well as protecting their health and well-being, is a challenge for governments and organizations providing education services. Constantly interacting with teachers to facilitate their return to the classroom will be an important component in getting students to return to the classroom. In this particular case, instructors request priority assistance during quarantine as well as during school reopening procedures, at least in the following areas:

Education, advice and resources for working on various forms of distance learning, including training in skills and use methodologies information and communication technology (ICT) and other platforms for distance learning and learning in education as well as contextual and flexible curriculum decisions, assessment and learning Training in feedback criteria for

is important that students receive support to sustain and develop advances in methodological innovation and the application of alternative forms of teaching, including opportunities to learn in

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a variety of settings . The impact on the psychological, social and emotional well-being of the education community has become more pronounced with COVID-19. In addition to living in overcrowded conditions for long periods of time, it also has serious effects on the mental health of the population as a whole.

For a large part of the population, confinement measures mean living in these conditions for a long time. Those working in education, families or communities have a responsibility to themselves and their clients to develop basic adaptive and emotional resilience abilities. In this context, socio-emotional learning is not only a necessary prerequisite for education, but also an extremely useful tool to mitigate the negative effects of the ongoing social and health crisis. To achieve this we will need accompaniment, support and resources specially modified for this purpose. The provision of resources for emotional support can be seen, for example, in some countries where the Ministry of Education (MINEDUC) has developed a set of socio-emotional support mechanisms targeted at the education community. This is just one example of providing resources for emotional support. Teachers were provided with guidelines for self-care and socio-emotional well-being in the context of a health crisis, as well as a teaching diary for the development of personal and autonomous socio-emotional learning based on their own experience (MINEDUC, 2020a).

The imperative to prioritize the most disadvantaged groups is inevitable in the context of the pandemic. The primary reason for this is to ensure that the existing conditions of inequality are not exacerbated.

There are also major gaps in access and achievement in ethnic and racial education in the region, resulting from historical and structural exclusion and discrimination affecting African and indigenous peoples (ECLAC/UNICEF, 2019; ECLAC, 2017 and 2018). These gaps result from the historical and structural exclusion and discrimination affecting indigenous peoples. The interaction of these vectors of social inequality fosters cyclical patterns of marginalization and risk exposure. Given that inequality has been brought to light and exacerbated by the pandemic, policy options designed for education in the current context must acknowledge the historic debt to these groups to guarantee their right to education, both in terms of availability and access. This is because

the pandemic has highlighted the problem of inequality and made it more severe (Vargas , 2019). In terms of continuity of education, it is noteworthy that culture, language, gender, gender, and accessibility are taken into account by the numerous needs and responses demanded by various groups.

10. Health After The Pandemic

Among these groups, which are most vulnerable to the effects of the pandemic and the ensuing health, social and economic crisis, the risk of school dropouts and dropouts is a special case that needs to be addressed . This is one of the situations that needs to be addressed. Steps must be taken now and over the next few months to prevent educational opportunities from being cut off completely. In the near term, efforts must be made to ensure that the children and adolescents most at risk of dropping out do not do so, and every possible means must be explored to encourage them to continue reading. Measures should be taken to ensure that students who cannot continue their education during this period do not experience any setbacks in terms of their general education experience or their ability to progress in their education. This needs to be done in the medium term. This requires coordination of actions such as removing redundancy, developing adaptive mechanisms for curriculum continuity, and implementing support strategies to restore lost ground and accelerate educational progress.

These education initiatives need to be supported by programs that provide social and financial safety nets as well as social and emotional support to children and their families. It is essential to coordinate the work with other policies in order to protect and secure the rights of children and to provide social protection to families with dependent children. This is necessary to assist families in precarious situations to the greatest extent possible.

11. Conclusion and Recommendations

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Relationships should be guided by solidarity and cooperation in the pursuit of the common good, and also by responsibility for the care of others as an essential component of one's own care and survival. The ongoing crisis has given new significance to social bonds, and these bonds serve as a basis for reconstructing identities and the meaning of citizenship, including on a global scale, revolving around the pragmatic goal of fostering the creation of the common . This can be achieved through daily community action, large and small, that recognizes and promotes togetherness as an essential component of building a shared future, without neglecting the dominant issues that divide communities. In this scenario and given the later stages of the pandemic, as well as the phenomena or processes of ongoing or future global crises such as climate change , key actors are increasingly emphasizing the need to rethink education and prioritize new content. It is necessary to prepare students to understand reality, to live and act together in times of crisis and uncertainty, to make decisions at the individual and family level, and to promote collective solutions to the pressing challenges that are bewildering communities. For example, key actors are increasingly emphasizing the need to prepare.

- (i) **Equality and inclusion:** emphasizing the most vulnerable and marginalized population groups such as indigenous peoples , refugees and migrants, persons with disabilities and the most socioeconomically disadvantaged populations, and sexual and gender diversity.
- (ii) **Quality and relevance:** focus on improving curriculum content (especially regarding health and well-being) and specific support for teachers, ensuring appropriate contracting and working conditions, teacher training for distance learning and back-to-school, socio -emotional support for working with students and their families
- (iii) **Education system:** readiness of the education system to respond to crises, ie resilience at all levels.
- (iv) **Interdisciplinary approaches:** The design and execution of this initiative focused not only on education but also on health, nutrition and social protection.
- (v) **Partnerships:** collaboration and collaboration between various sectors and players to develop an integrated system that focuses primarily on students and education staff .

These problems, which represent the necessity of fulfilling the right to education in particular, are encountered in education and social protection systems as well as states. As a result, there must be sufficient resources to appropriately allocate and distribute the budget. The real financial repercussions may not be recognized until 2021, as the economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic is still emerging and the recovery may take longer. Therefore, it is essential to calculate the costs of national education systems and to prioritize expenditures. Today, these challenges and lessons provide an opportunity to reconsider the purpose of education and its role in preserving human life and dignity, to ensure that no one is left behind. This crisis provides a once-in-a-generation opportunity to strengthen the resilience of national education systems and transform them into equitable and inclusive systems that contribute to meeting the collective commitment made in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. This crisis offers an unprecedented chance to do so, as countries consider the best way to face uncertainties and safely reopen their educational institutions.

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